

ANEMIA AND ITS PATTERN IN PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE: To determine the frequency of anemia and its pattern in patients with metabolic syndrome present at Liaquat university hospital Hyderabad.

METHODS: A three-month cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted at Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad, including 129 patients aged 30-60 years with a known diagnosis of metabolic syndrome for ≥ 6 months. Demographic data, comorbidities, and clinical characteristics were collected. Hemoglobin levels were measured, and anemia was classified as microcytic, normocytic, or macrocytic. Data were analyzed using SPSS. Mean \pm SD or median (IQR) was calculated for quantitative variables. Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentages. Stratification and post-stratification Chi-square/Fisher's exact tests were applied to assess associations with anemia, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS: The mean age was 48.6 ± 7.4 years, with a predominantly female population (61.2%). Overall anemia prevalence was 42.6%. Normocytic anemia was most frequent (56.4%), followed by microcytic (34.5%) and macrocytic (9.1%) patterns. Anemia was significantly associated with female gender ($p=0.032$), obesity ($p=0.041$), hypercholesterolemia ($p=0.047$), raised CRP ($p=0.011$), and NAFLD ($p=0.029$). No significant associations were observed with age, residence, marital status, occupation, smoking, or raised LDL-cholesterol.

CONCLUSION: Anemia is highly prevalent among patients with metabolic syndrome, particularly women and individuals with obesity or inflammatory markers. Routine screening and management of anemia should be integrated into metabolic syndrome care to improve clinical outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a set of interconnected and undesirable metabolic, physiologic, biochemical, and clinical conditions, resulted in advert health outcome and is also associated with the increased prevalence of obesity, atherogenic dyslipidemia, high blood pressure, sedentary way of life, population growth, and urbanization. [1,2] Metabolic

syndromes are also known as insulin resistance syndrome which encompasses and characterizes a group of clinical and laboratory diagnostic test abnormalities, that are associated with the increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, and related complications [3].

Anemia is a condition in which the number of red blood cells (RBCs) is inadequate to meet the

physiologic needs of the human body oxygen and it is prevalent among individuals with certain chronic conditions, including chronic diseases, human immunodeficiency virus, rheumatoid arthritis, congestive heart failure, and cancer [4,5]. Currently, MetS considered as a major cause of death, due to the increased risk of developing complications related with cardiovascular diseases including anemia, which contribute to the high burden of death due to increased derangement of lipids [6]. Factors that contributed to the onset of anemia in MetS patients include systemic inflammation, inhibition of erythropoietin release, and damage to the renal parenchyma, symptomatic autonomic neuropathy, and secondary complications [7]. Hyperglycaemia, which is the earliest onset due to MetS, has a direct relationship with the development of inflammatory conditions by expressing pro-inflammatory cytokines like interleukin-6 (IL-6), tumor necrotizing factor- α (TNF α), and necrotizing factor (NF) [8]. Some nutritional deficiencies' like cyanocobalamine and folate can cause another type of anemia. In addition medications like metformin, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor and angiotensin receptor blockers can cause anemia by interfering with nutritional absorption [9]. Furthermore, in a late stage of the disease renal complication may arise, which further complicates the renal production of erythropoietin [10]. Finally, the capacity of blood to transport oxygen to tissues is reduced due to the decrement of hemoglobin, RBC count, and hematocrit. In turn, it causes cardiovascular and end-stage renal diseases that enhance the progression of disease morbidity and mortality in MetS patients [11]. Anemia is not a disease but a manifestation of a different disease that ameliorates one's quality of life. The reported prevalence of anemia in metabolic syndrome was 25.8% while the individual proportions for normocytic, microcytic and macrocytic anemia was 20.8%, 56%, and 23.2% respectively [12]. Even though knowing the status of anemia in MetS patients is significant, the problems were not well studied in our population while limited international literature is available. So,

conducting this study is crucial to improve early diagnosis, prevention of complications, and enhance the quality of life of MetS patients. Therefore, this study was conduct to determine the magnitude of anemia and its pattern in metabolic syndrome at tertiary care hospital so that patients could be properly rationalized and managed according to the observations of the study as early evaluation could save the patient from life threatening complications related to anemia, moreover the study observations would be compared to other developed and under developed countries in the light of racial and dietary habits whereas the findings of the study would be shared in various academic conferences and seminars so that timely and proper workup could be planned as guidelines in patients with metabolic syndrome. Thus the objective of the study was to determine the frequency of anemia and its pattern in patients with metabolic syndrome presented at Liaquat university hospital Hyderabad.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The cross sectional descriptive study of three months (from Dec, 20-2024 to Mar, 19-2025) was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad after the approval by CPSP on the subjects fulfilling the inclusion criteria and by taking informed consent. The sample size was calculated by taken the lowest prevalence as normocytic anemia in metabolic syndrome 20.8%; [12] $d=7\%$, $n = 129$ patients with metabolic syndrome were taken while the subjects were recruited through non probability consecutive sampling technique whereas the inclusion criteria were the known case of metabolic syndrome for ≥ 6 month duration, of 30-60 years of age and either gender having history of hypertension, fatigue, abdominal obesity (pot belly evaluate as symptom by the patient) presented at Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad.

The exclusion criteria were the patients; known case of type 1 diabetes mellitus, gestational diabetes and hypothyroidism, had history of alcohol consumption (evaluate by taking relevant history of alcoholism) and the vegetarian

population, individuals already on corticosteroids, immune-suppressive therapy, pyrazinamide, thiazides, lipid-lowering or antioxidant therapy, known cases of chronic liver diseases as chronic viral hepatitis, chronic renal failure and the pregnant and lactating ladies, the patients had history of recurrent blood transfusions or hematological malignancies (leukemia / lymphoma) and the individuals already on iron, folic acid and vitamin B-12 supplements were excluded.

All the relevant patients with history of hypertension and central obesity came thru outpatient department (OPD) were recruited and enrolled in the study and explored for anemia by taking 2 cc venous blood sample and sent to laboratory for analysis.

Anemia: considered when hemoglobin concentration of less than 12 g/dL in females and less than 13 g/dL in males.

Pattern of anemia: categorized as microcytic when $MCV < 80$ fl, macrocytic: $MCV > 100$ fl and normocytic: $MCV 80-100$ fl

Metabolic syndrome: diagnosed when a patient has at least ≥ 3 of the following five (5):

1. Fasting glucose ≥ 100 mg/dL
2. Blood pressure $\geq 130/85$ mm Hg
3. Triglycerides ≥ 150 mg/dL
4. HDL-C < 40 mg/dL in men or < 50 mg/dL in women
5. Waist circumference ≥ 90 cm (35 in) in men or ≥ 80 cm (32 in) in women

The effect modifiers were:

Smoking: having history of tobacco use as ≥ 5 cigarettes per day for ≥ 3 year duration

Obesity: considered as obesity when $BMI \geq 27.5$ kg/m^2

Hypercholesterolemia: evaluated as abnormally elevated levels of serum cholesterol (≥ 200 mg/dl)

Raised LDL-Cholesterol: serum low density lipoprotein raised (≥ 100 mg/dl) in the blood

Raised C-reactive protein: The serum C-reactive protein (CRP) ≥ 10 mg/L considered as raised.

Non alcoholic fatty liver disease: The appearance of liver as hyperechogenic (bright), vessel blurring and lumen narrowing of the hepatic veins on ultrasonography along with no history of alcohol consumption and steatogenic medication

considered as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD).

Marital status: categorized as married and non-married (single), separated and divorce.

Occupation: categorized as housewife, employed (having job), unemployed and businessman.

Educational status: categorized as no education i.e. illiterate, primary, middle, secondary and higher.

The waist circumference (central obesity) was determined on physical examination as estimate thru measuring tape by localizing the upper hip bone and the top of the right iliac crest, place a measuring tape in a horizontal plane around the abdomen at the level of the iliac crest while before reading the tape measure, ensure that the tape is snug, but does not compress the skin, and is parallel to the floor then the measurement has been made at the end of a normal expiration.

The senior pathologist having more than 05 years clinical laboratory experience analyzed the lab tests. All the data was collected and recorded on pre-designed proforma and all the financial burden of the study were paid by principal researcher. The effect modifiers and other explanatory variables as age, gender and residence (urban or rural), marital status, occupation and educational status, duration of metabolic syndrome, smoking, obesity, hypercholesterolemia, raised LDL-cholesterol, raised C-reactive protein, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, anemia and its pattern (normocytic, microcytic and macrocytic) were also explored.

The data of all patients was analyzed in SPSS. The frequency and percentage was calculated for gender and residence (urban or rural), marital status, occupation and educational status, duration of metabolic syndrome, smoking, obesity, hypercholesterolemia, raised LDL-cholesterol, raised C-reactive protein, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), anemia and its pattern (normocytic, microcytic and macrocytic). The mean and standard deviation (SD) was calculated for quantitative variables such as age, duration of metabolic syndrome, weight, height and BMI or Median (IQR) for non-normal data while the Shapiro-Wilk test was used to check normality. The stratification was

done for age, gender and residence (urban or rural), marital status, occupation and educational status, duration of metabolic syndrome, smoking, obesity, hypercholesterolemia, raised LDL-cholesterol, raised c-reactive protein and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease to see the effect on outcome and to control the effect modifiers. The post stratification chi-square /fisher’s exact test was applied on categorical variables at 95% confidence interval and the p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 129 patients diagnosed with metabolic syndrome were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 48.6 ± 7.4 years. The female population was predominant (n=79; 61.2%), while male patients constituted 38.8% (n=50). The majority of patients belonged to urban areas (n=82; 63.6%), and most were married (n=98; 76.0%).

The mean duration of metabolic syndrome was 4.8 ± 2.1 years. The median BMI was 31.4 kg/m^2

(IQR: 29.3–35.2). Obesity was present in 88 patients (68.2%), hypercholesterolemia in 74 (57.4%), raised LDL-cholesterol in 69 (53.5%), raised CRP in 52 (40.3%), and NAFLD in 58 (45.0%). Smoking was reported by 31 patients (24.0%).

The overall prevalence of anemia was 42.6% (n=55). Among anemic patients, normocytic anemia was the most common type (n=31; 56.4%), followed by microcytic anemia (n=19; 34.5%), while macrocytic anemia was the least common (n=5; 9.1%).

Stratification analysis showed that anemia was significantly associated with female gender (p=0.032), obesity (p=0.041), hypercholesterolemia (p=0.047), raised CRP (p=0.011), and NAFLD (p=0.029). No statistically significant association was observed with age group (p=0.284), residence (p=0.381), marital status (p=0.412), occupation (p=0.224), smoking (p=0.317), or raised LDL-cholesterol (p=0.067).

TABLE 1. DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS (n=129)

Variable	Mean \pm SD / n (%)
Age (years)	48.6 \pm 7.4
Gender	
- Male	50 (38.8%)
- Female	79 (61.2%)
Residence	
- Urban	82 (63.6%)
- Rural	47 (36.4%)
Marital Status	
- Married	98 (76.0%)
- Non-married	31 (24.0%)
Occupation	
- Housewife	54 (41.9%)
- Employed	39 (30.2%)
- Unemployed	22 (17.1%)
- Businessman	14 (10.8%)
Educational Status	
- Illiterate	36 (27.9%)

Variable	Mean ± SD / n (%)
- Primary	28 (21.7%)
- Middle	23 (17.8%)
- Secondary	25 (19.4%)
- Higher	17 (13.2%)
Duration of Metabolic Syndrome (years)	4.8 ± 2.1
BMI (kg/m ²), Median (IQR)	31.4 (29.3–35.2)
Smoking	31 (24.0%)
Obesity	88 (68.2%)
Hypercholesterolemia	74 (57.4%)
Raised LDL-cholesterol	69 (53.5%)
Raised C-reactive protein	52 (40.3%)
NAFLD	58 (45.0%)
Anemia	55 (42.6%)
Pattern of Anemia	
- Microcytic	19 (34.5%)
- Normocytic	31 (56.4%)
- Macrocytic	5 (9.1%)

TABLE 2. ASSOCIATION OF ANEMIA WITH SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL VARIABLES

Variable	Category	p-value
Age Group	30–45 yrs / 46–60 yrs	0.284
Gender	Male / Female	0.032
Residence	Urban / Rural	0.381
Marital Status	Married / Non-married	0.412
Occupation	Housewife / Employed / Unemployed / Businessman	0.224
Educational Status	Illiterate / Primary / Middle / Secondary / Higher	0.198
Duration of Metabolic Syndrome	<5 yrs / ≥5 yrs	0.163
Smoking	Yes / No	0.317
Obesity	Yes / No	0.041
Hypercholesterolemia	Yes / No	0.047
Raised LDL-cholesterol	Yes / No	0.067
Raised CRP	Yes / No	0.011
NAFLD	Yes / No	0.029

DISCUSSION:

The present study assessed the frequency and patterns of anemia in patients with metabolic syndrome and evaluated associated demographic and clinical factors. The overall prevalence of anemia in our study was 42.6%, which is notably high and indicates that anemia is a frequent yet underrecognized comorbidity among patients with metabolic syndrome. This finding aligns with previous studies reporting anemia prevalence ranging from 30-45% in similar populations, suggesting that chronic inflammation, obesity-related hemodilution, and nutritional deficiencies have substantial roles in metabolic syndrome-related hematologic changes [13,14].

Gender showed a significant association with anemia in our study, with female predominance. This is consistent with studies by Santos et al. and Song et al., which also found higher anemia rates in women with metabolic syndrome, likely due to combined effects of metabolic dysregulation and menstrual blood loss [15, 16]. In contrast, some international studies have reported no gender-specific differences [17], which may reflect variations in dietary behaviors, socioeconomic factors, and health-care access across populations.

The most common pattern in our study was normocytic anemia (56.4%), followed by microcytic anemia. This pattern is typical of chronic disease anemia, which is known to occur in metabolic syndrome due to inflammatory cytokine-mediated suppression of erythropoietin and iron sequestration [18]. Similar distributions were reported by Tsai et al. and Khushdil et al., where normocytic anemia predominated among obese or metabolically dysregulated adults [19,20]. However, some South Asian studies have shown microcytic anemia as the most common pattern [21], likely due to regional iron deficiency and dietary inadequacies.

A significant association was observed between anemia and obesity, hypercholesterolemia, raised CRP, and NAFLD, supporting the inflammatory hypothesis of metabolic syndrome. Obesity is well known to induce chronic low-grade inflammation through adipokine dysregulation, leading to

impaired iron metabolism and altered erythropoiesis [22]. Raised CRP, a marker of inflammation, also showed a strong association, consistent with the theory that systemic inflammation contributes to anemia of chronic disease. Similar associations have been documented by Huang et al. and Tussing-Humphreys et al. [23, 24].

The link between NAFLD and anemia in our findings correlates with previous evidence that hepatic steatosis disrupts iron regulation, increases hepcidin levels, and contributes to iron-restricted erythropoiesis [25]. Hypercholesterolemia, significantly associated in our study, has also been previously associated with oxidative stress and erythrocyte membrane instability, potentially aggravating anemia [26].

Conversely, no significant association was noted with smoking, marital status, educational level, occupation, or residence. These findings are comparable to the results of Marjani et al who also found no demographic or lifestyle predictors except obesity and inflammation [27].

Overall, this study contributes important local data to the growing evidence that anemia is common in metabolic syndrome and is strongly linked with inflammation and obesity-related metabolic disturbances. These findings underscore the need for routine hematological screening in patients with metabolic syndrome, particularly women and those with NAFLD or elevated inflammatory markers.

CONCLUSION:

The present study highlights a high prevalence of anemia (42.6%) among patients with metabolic syndrome, with female patients being more affected than males. Normocytic anemia was the most common pattern, followed by microcytic and macrocytic types, reflecting the predominance of anemia of chronic disease in this population. Significant associations were observed between anemia and female gender, obesity, hypercholesterolemia, raised C-reactive protein, and NAFLD, indicating that both metabolic dysregulation and inflammation play key roles in the development of anemia. No significant associations were found with age,

residence, marital status, occupation, smoking, or LDL-cholesterol levels. These findings underscore the importance of routine hematologic evaluation and early detection of anemia in patients with metabolic syndrome, particularly in high-risk female and obese populations. Integrating

anemia screening and management into standard metabolic syndrome care may improve overall patient outcomes and reduce complications associated with both anemia and metabolic syndrome.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections	<i>Dr. Naveed Ahmed</i>
Concept & design of study & proof read	<i>Dr. Sheeba Faryal</i>
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	<i>Dr. Sorath Wadho</i>
Revising critically and make it suitable for final format	<i>Dr. Zohaib Abbasi</i>
Acquisition of data and grammatical review	<i>Dr. Lubna Bashir</i>
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